

Order Restricted Cluster Randomized Design

Dalton Hopper*

Omer Ozturk[†]

Abstract

This research develops inference for the order restricted cluster randomized design (ORCRD). For H treatment levels, this design consists of H blocks, each of which contains m sets of H ranked cluster units. These cluster units are then organized into a row-column structure. In this structure, rows are indexed by two variables: block and set. Columns are indexed by rank only. The block and rank indices define H^2 cells. The H treatments are then randomly allocated to these H^2 cells with the restriction that each treatment appears only once in each block and column (rank). The cluster units in each cell receive the corresponding treatment. The data is collected from subsampling in each cluster unit by using ranked set sampling. For this design, we fit a linear model that accounts for the correlation structure among cluster units in the same set, calculate EMS expressions, develop inference for the treatment effect, assess ranking effectiveness, and estimate model parameters.

Key Words: order restricted randomization, ranked set sampling, intracluster correlation coefficient, Latin square, nested factor, random effect, mixed effect model

1. Background Information

Some research projects aim to assess intervention effects of a methodology or policy on a collective body rather than on individual experimental units (EUs). If this is the case, the design may require randomizing treatments to cluster units instead of subjects within clusters (Moberg and Kramer, 2015). A design characterized by this type of randomization scheme is referred to as a cluster randomized design (CRD).

Cluster randomized designs are often more practical than completely randomized designs. CRDs have been used to evaluate various programs; some examples include health treatment programs (Menya et al., 2015; Cundill et al., 2015), vaccination programs (Roca et al., 2011), and educational intervention programs (Wing et al., 2015; Tol et al., 2014). Cluster randomized designs also mitigate effects of contamination (Moberg and Kramer, 2015).

Cluster randomized designs are certainly beneficial in many ways, but they also have their share of disadvantages. For example, a CRD generally has a smaller statistical power than a completely randomized design with the same number of subjects (Kramer et al., 2009). This is because subjects in the same cluster unit of a CRD are usually more similar than subjects in different cluster units. Similarity of within-cluster units is typically measured by the intracluster correlation coefficient (ICC). The ICC can be written as $ICC = \gamma^2 / (\sigma^2 + \gamma^2)$, where γ^2 and σ^2 represent the between-cluster variance and within-cluster variance, respectively. Planning a cluster randomized design is also more complex than planning a completely randomized design, since a CRD has two sample sizes to consider (number of cluster units and number of within-cluster units). Turner et al. (2017a,b) performed a literature review on the design and analysis of CRDs. Together, these articles update the review published by Murray et al. (2004).

Cluster populations often have auxiliary information that, prior to treatment allocation, can be used to rank a small set of units without full measurement. Incorporating this information into a CRD yields a more efficient design. Wang et al. (2016) used this ranking

*The Ohio State University, 281 W. Lane Avenue, Columbus, OH 43202

[†]The Ohio State University, 281 W. Lane Avenue, Columbus, OH 43202

information to construct a two-level hierarchical linear model for a CRD in which ranked set sampling (RSS) is used at the cluster level or subsampling level (or both). Ozturk et al. (2023a) also examined an RSS-structured CRD, namely the cluster randomized ranked design (CRRD). However, they looked at the problem from a design perspective, treating ranking groups as a blocking factor.

Ranked set sampling is a very useful procedure. While simple random samples are, *on average*, representative of the population, an individual SRS might not accurately reflect the true values in a population. Some sampling methods that have been developed to address this issue are stratified, cluster, and proportional sampling, but these techniques utilize additional population information *a priori* (Hollander et al., 2013). Ranked set sampling, however, does not require additional population information until after EUs are sampled. It uses the positions (ranks) of unmeasured units in a small set to decide which unit should be selected for full measurement. This process creates homogeneous ranking groups, which generally results in a sample that is more representative of the population than a SRS. The ranking procedure used in RSS is acceptable so long as it does not require full measurement of the EUs. Some examples of valid ranking mechanisms are visual inspection, an auxiliary variable, and expert opinion. For a comprehensive summary of work that has been done with ranked set sampling, the reader is referred to Wolfe (2012), Bouza-Herrera and Al-Omari (2018), and the references therein.

While RSS is an advantageous procedure, it may cause logistical challenges in practice. In a set of size H , for example, RSS retains only one experimental unit. The other $H - 1$ units are used for ranking but are then discarded. If there are a limited number of EUs available for sampling or if the cost of sampling is high, this limitation can be a significant one. To address this problem, Ozturk and MacEachern (2004) introduced order restricted randomization (ORR) for the estimation of contrast parameters in a completely randomized design.

ORR involves ranking and quantifying all EUs in a set to create two blocking variables: set and ranking group. If the ranking process is accurate, the use of ranking group as a blocking factor effectively reduces the variability in an experiment and improves the efficiency of the design. The ranking mechanism is not restrictive: it only requires an assessment of the relative position of units in a set. The ranking process results in a positive correlation of EUs in the same set. Units in different sets are independent. The treatments are allocated to EUs in such a way that all ranks appear the same number of times in each treatment regime. The treatment allocation, along with the positive correlation among within-set EUs, reduces the variance of pairwise treatment contrast estimators. Ozturk and MacEachern developed statistical inference for ORR designs (Ozturk and MacEachern, 2004, 2007, 2013). Ozturk et al. (2023b) proposed an ORR design with a Latin square structure.

In this paper, we introduce the order restricted cluster randomized design (ORCRD)—a more efficient design than CRDs in the current literature. The ORCRD is a two-stage design that incorporates ORR at the cluster level (to our knowledge, this is not covered in the current literature) and RSS at the subsampling level. The ORCRD is similar to a traditional CRD but adds two blocking factors, one of which comes from ranking cluster units in small comparison sets. The other block can be any factor that divides the cluster population into homogeneous groups. For example, if schools are the cluster units, this blocking factor might be location or type of school (public or private).

We note that if the ranking mechanisms involve quantitative auxiliary variables, these variables can be used as covariates in a covariance analysis. However, an analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) model requires strong assumptions that blocking does not. For example, an ANCOVA model assumes normality of error terms and linearity between the response

and covariate, while the construction of ranking groups only requires a consistent ranking procedure (explained in Section 2.1).

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 delineates the ORCRD, introduces a general model for this design under a consistent ranking scheme, and proposes one-parameter ranking models for the cluster and individual error terms. Section 3 contains an analysis of variance (ANOVA) table. The expected mean square (EMS) expressions are used to construct an approximate F -test for the treatment effect. Type I error and power simulations are discussed as well. Section 4 assesses ranking effectiveness in two ways: through the magnitude of F -statistics for the cluster and subsampling level ranking effects and through the restricted maximum likelihood (REML) parameter estimates of cluster and subsampling level ranking correlations. Section 5 provides concluding remarks.

2. Introduction of the ORCRD

We assume that the cluster population can be separated into H_1 blocks. The order restricted cluster randomized design (ORCRD) starts with a block design that uses these H_1 blocks. In each block, we construct m sets, each of size H_1 . Cluster units are entered into the design as follows: from block 1, H_1 cluster units are randomly selected and ranked from smallest to largest using pre-experimental information. These cluster units make up the first set in block 1. Next, an additional H_1 cluster units are randomly selected from the same block and ranked from smallest to largest. These cluster units comprise the second set in block 1. The process of selecting sets of H_1 cluster units and ranking them is continued until there are m sets of ranked cluster units in block 1. The same procedure is repeated for the remaining blocks. This results in $H_1 m$ sets of H_1 ranked cluster units, so there are a total of $H_1^2 m$ cluster units in the design. Because of the ranking mechanism, clusters in the same set are correlated; however, clusters in different sets are independent.

The cluster units are then organized into a row-column structure. The rows in this structure are indexed by two attributes: block and set. Columns are indexed by only one attribute: rank. The block and rank indices define H_1^2 cells, each of which contains m cluster units. The H_1 treatments are randomly assigned to the H_1^2 cells with the restriction that each treatment appears only once in each block and ranking group.

Table 1 illustrates one particular treatment allocation scheme of the ORCRD. In this table, T_h represents treatment h ; CU_{ikhr} denotes the cluster unit in set r of block i that is assigned rank k and treatment h . The m cluster units in block i and ranking group k define a cell (i, k) . We note that the treatment allocation is performed on cells, not on clusters within a cell. Hence, all cluster units in the same cell receive the same treatment.

Each cluster unit in an ORCRD contains a population of within-cluster units. Since it is often not feasible to measure a response for all within-cluster EUs in an experiment, we use ranked set sampling to select p EUs from each cluster unit. The process of obtaining a RSS of p subjects in one cluster unit, CU_{ikhr} , is explained below:

1. Specify a set size H_2 and cycle size d_2 such that $p = H_2 d_2$.
2. Randomly select $p H_2$ subjects from cluster unit CU_{ikhr} .
3. Partition these $p H_2$ subjects into p sets of size H_2 .
4. Rank the subjects in each of these p sets from smallest to largest using any available procedure that does not require full measurement, such as visual inspection, an auxiliary variable, or expert opinion.

Table 1: ORCRD with $H_1 = 3$ and m cluster units in each cell

Block (i)	Set (r)	Cluster Rank (k)		
		1	2	3
1	1	$T_1 : CU_{1111}$	$T_2 : CU_{1221}$	$T_3 : CU_{1331}$
	2	$T_1 : CU_{1112}$	$T_2 : CU_{1222}$	$T_3 : CU_{1332}$
	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
	m	$T_1 : CU_{111m}$	$T_2 : CU_{122m}$	$T_3 : CU_{133m}$
2	1	$T_2 : CU_{2121}$	$T_3 : CU_{2231}$	$T_1 : CU_{2311}$
	2	$T_2 : CU_{2122}$	$T_3 : CU_{2232}$	$T_1 : CU_{2312}$
	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
	m	$T_2 : CU_{212m}$	$T_3 : CU_{223m}$	$T_1 : CU_{231m}$
3	1	$T_3 : CU_{3131}$	$T_1 : CU_{3211}$	$T_2 : CU_{3321}$
	2	$T_3 : CU_{3132}$	$T_1 : CU_{3212}$	$T_2 : CU_{3322}$
	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
	m	$T_3 : CU_{313m}$	$T_1 : CU_{321m}$	$T_2 : CU_{332m}$

- Retain the subject with rank 1 from the first d_2 sets. Retain the subject with rank 2 from the next d_2 sets. Continue this process, and retain the subject with rank H_2 from the last d_2 sets.

Table 2 provides a visual representation of responses obtained using RSS in one cell of an ORCRD. It is clear that each cluster unit, CU_{ikhr} , $r = 1, \dots, m$, in cell (i, k) contains $p = H_2 d_2$ response measurements.

Cluster units in cell (i, k)					
Set (r)	Within-cluster rank (v)	Responses			
1 (CU_{ikh1})	1	Y_{ikh111}	Y_{ikh112}	\dots	Y_{ikh11d_2}
	2	Y_{ikh121}	Y_{ikh122}	\dots	Y_{ikh12d_2}
	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\dots	\vdots
	H_2	Y_{ikh1H_21}	Y_{ikh1H_22}	\dots	$Y_{ikh1H_2d_2}$
2 (CU_{ikh2})	1	Y_{ikh211}	Y_{ikh212}	\dots	Y_{ikh21d_2}
	2	Y_{ikh221}	Y_{ikh222}	\dots	Y_{ikh22d_2}
	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\dots	\vdots
	H_2	Y_{ikh2H_21}	Y_{ikh2H_22}	\dots	$Y_{ikh2H_2d_2}$
\vdots		\vdots	\vdots	\dots	\vdots
m (CU_{ikhm})	1	Y_{ikhm11}	Y_{ikhm12}	\dots	Y_{ikhm1d_2}
	2	Y_{ikhm21}	Y_{ikhm22}	\dots	Y_{ikhm2d_2}
	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\dots	\vdots
	H_2	Y_{ikhmH_21}	Y_{ikhmH_22}	\dots	$Y_{ikhmH_2d_2}$

Table 2: Responses, Y_{ikhrvs} , obtained using RSS within cluster units CU_{ikhr} , $r = 1, \dots, m$, in cell (i, k) of an ORCRD

2.1 Models and Assumptions Under a General Judgment Ranking Scheme

We propose the following model for the ORCRD:

$$Y_{ikhrvs} = \mu + \alpha_i + \gamma\phi_k^* + \beta_h + \tau d_{r(i)} + \gamma c_{r(ik)}^* + \sigma\omega_v^* + \sigma\epsilon_{sv(ikr)}^*, \quad i, k, h = 1, \dots, H_1; \\ r = 1, \dots, m; v = 1, \dots, H_2; s = 1, \dots, d_2; p = H_2 d_2; h = b(i, k). \quad (1)$$

The notation $h = b(i, k)$ indicates that the ORCRD does not include observations for all possible combinations of i , k , and h , where h is the treatment level assigned to block i and cluster level ranking group k .

We now define the terms and assumptions of model (1): μ is the overall mean; α_i is the i^{th} block effect (factor A); β_h is the h^{th} treatment effect (factor B); ϕ_k^* is the k^{th} cluster level ranking group effect (factor C); ω_v^* is the v^{th} subsampling ranking group effect (factor S); $d_{r(i)}$ is the r^{th} set effect nested within block i (factor $D(A)$); $c_{r(ik)}^*$ is the error term for cluster r nested within cell (i, k) ; and $\epsilon_{sv(ikr)}^*$ is the error term for the subject in subsampling cycle s with subsampling rank v in cluster r of cell (i, k) . The factors A , B , C , and S are fixed effects that satisfy the following sum-to-zero constraints: $\sum_{i=1}^{H_1} \alpha_i = 0$, $\sum_{h=1}^{H_1} \beta_h = 0$, $\sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^* = 0$, and $\sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^* = 0$. Factor $D(A)$, the cluster error, and the individual error are treated as random. The set effect, $d_{r(i)}$, is assumed to follow a standard normal distribution. The cluster error term, $c_{r(ik)}^*$, is the k^{th} judgment order statistic (with shifted mean 0) in a set of size H_1 from a standard normal distribution; the mean is shifted to ϕ_k^* . The individual error term, $\epsilon_{sv(ikr)}^*$, is the v^{th} judgment order statistic (with shifted mean 0) in a set of size H_2 from a standard normal distribution; the mean is shifted to ω_v^* . We assume mutual independence among $d_{r(i)}$, $c_{r(ik)}^*$, and $\epsilon_{sv(ikr)}^*$.

In the ORCRD, the method by which within-set cluster error terms are ranked can be subjective and imprecise, but it should satisfy some consistency condition. The ranking mechanism is consistent if it satisfies the following condition:

$$F(y) = \frac{1}{H_1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} F_k^*(y), \quad (2)$$

where $F(y)$ and $F_k^*(y)$ are the cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of a standard normal random variable and the k^{th} judgment order statistic in a set of size H_1 from a standard normal distribution, respectively. The consistency condition in equation (2) holds if the same ranking procedure is used in each set and a unique rank is assigned to each unit in a set (Presnell and Bohn, 1999). In general, the form of $F_k^*(y)$ in equation (2) is unknown; it depends on the ranking mechanism.

The arguments in the previous paragraph hold for the subsampling level ranking method as well, with appropriate adjustments in notation. These arguments are valid regardless of cluster and subsampling level ranking qualities. However, the efficiency of the ORCRD increases as ranking qualities improve. In the next subsection, we introduce one-parameter ranking models for stage 1 and 2 sampling. The ranking qualities are controlled by the magnitudes of the parameters in these ranking models.

2.2 One-Parameter Ranking Models

We assume there exists an auxiliary variable, W , that is correlated with the unordered cluster errors and can be used to rank the cluster units prior to treatment allocation. We then model the mean-corrected judgment ranked cluster error term for each Y_{ikhrvs} as

$$c_{r(ik)}^*(\rho_1) = \sqrt{1 - \rho_1^2} u_{r(ik)} + \rho_1 w_{r(ik)}^+ - \rho_1 \phi_k. \quad (3)$$

In this model, ρ_1 is the correlation between the unordered cluster error term, $c_{r(ik)}$, and the corresponding W value, $w_{r(ik)}$; $u_{r(ik)} \stackrel{\text{ind}}{\sim} N(0, 1)$; $w_{r(ik)}^+$ is the k^{th} order statistic in a set of size H_1 from a standard normal distribution; and $\phi_k = E(w_{r(ik)}^+)$. The quantity $u_{r(ik)}$ serves as a noise variable in this model. The parameter ρ_1 controls the quality of ranking. For smaller values of ρ_1 , obtaining an accurate ranking becomes more difficult.

For example, if $\rho_1 = 0$, $c_{r(i_k)}^*(\rho_1) = u_{r(i_k)}$; i.e., $c_{r(i_k)}^*(\rho_1)$ is a standard normal random variable that does not involve $w_{r(i_k)}^+$. Hence, ranking $c_{r(i_k)}^*(\rho_1)$ with respect to $w_{r(i_k)}^+$ would be completely at random. If $\rho_1 = 1$, $c_{r(i_k)}^*(\rho_1) = w_{r(i_k)}^+ - \phi_k$; i.e., $c_{r(i_k)}^*(\rho_1)$ is a mean-corrected order statistic in a set of size H_1 from a standard normal distribution. In this case, ranking with respect to $w_{r(i_k)}^+$ would be without error. Other ranking qualities can be represented using appropriate values of ρ_1 .

We also assume there exists an auxiliary variable, Z , that is correlated with the unordered subsampling errors and can be used to rank within-cluster EUs. We model the mean-corrected judgment ranked subsampling error term for each Y_{ikhrvs} as

$$\epsilon_{sv(ikr)}^*(\rho_2) = \sqrt{1 - \rho_2^2} u_{sv(ikr)} + \rho_2 z_{sv(ikr)}^+ - \rho_2 \omega_v. \quad (4)$$

In this model, ρ_2 is the correlation between the unordered subsampling error term, $\epsilon_{sv(ikr)}$, and the corresponding Z value, $z_{sv(ikr)}$; $u_{sv(ikr)} \stackrel{\text{ind}}{\sim} N(0, 1)$; $z_{sv(ikr)}^+$ is the v^{th} order statistic in a set of size H_2 from a standard normal distribution; and $\omega_v = E(z_{sv(ikr)}^+)$.

Under the above consistent ranking models, we rewrite model (1) as

$$Y_{ikhrvs} = \mu + \alpha_i + \rho_1 \gamma \phi_k + \beta_h + \tau d_{r(i)} + \gamma c_{r(i_k)}^*(\rho_1) + \rho_2 \sigma \omega_v + \sigma \epsilon_{sv(ikr)}^*(\rho_2), \\ i, k, h = 1, \dots, H_1; r = 1, \dots, m; v = 1, \dots, H_2; s = 1, \dots, d_2; p = H_2 d_2; h = b(i, k). \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) defines a linear model that partitions the total variation into different sources. In the next section, we provide an ANOVA table that includes the expected mean squares for these sources of variation.

3. Statistical Inference for Treatment Effect

3.1 Analysis of Variance

The total experimental variation under model (5) is partitioned the same way as in any standard ANOVA model. Table 3 contains the EMS expressions under this model. Unlike the EMS expressions for a traditional CRD, the EMS expressions for the ORCRD depend on the ranking models in equations (3) and (4). The impact of ranking can be seen from these EMS expressions. For example, as ρ_1 increases, the expected mean squared cluster error decreases. As ρ_2 increases, the expected mean squared error and expected mean squared cluster error both decrease. We note that if we ignore the rank and set effects, the ORCRD reduces to a cluster randomized block design. If the block effect is ignored as well, the design reduces to a traditional CRD.

3.2 Approximate F -test for Treatment Effect

The EMS expressions in Table 3 suggest a testing procedure for the treatment effect. Consider the null hypothesis of no treatment effect versus the alternative hypothesis of some treatment effect:

$$H_0 : \beta_h - \beta_1 = 0 \text{ for all } h = 2, \dots, H_1 \text{ versus } H_a : \text{at least two of the } \beta_h \text{'s differ.}$$

The test statistic, F_B , is as follows:

$$F_B = \frac{MSB}{MSCE}.$$

Table 3: EMS expressions for model (5)

Source	df	EMS
<i>A</i>	$H_1 - 1$	$\sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 + H_1 p\tau^2 + \frac{H_1 m p}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{i=1}^{H_1} \alpha_i^2$
<i>B</i>	$H_1 - 1$	$\sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right) + \frac{H_1 m p}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{h=1}^{H_1} \beta_h^2$
<i>C</i>	$H_1 - 1$	$\sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2(1-H_1 m)}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right)$
<i>D(A)</i>	$H_1(m - 1)$	$\sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 + H_1 p\tau^2$
Cluster Error (<i>CE</i>)	$(H_1 m - 2)(H_1 - 1)$	$\sigma_S^2 + p\gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2\right)$
<i>S</i>	$H_2 - 1$	$\sigma_S^2 + \frac{H_1^2 m d_2}{H_2 - 1} \rho_2^2 \sigma^2 \sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^2$
Residual Error (<i>E</i>)	$H_1^2 m(p - 1) - (H_2 - 1)$	σ_S^2

Note: $\sigma_S^2 = \sigma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_2^2}{H_2} \sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^2\right)$

The null distribution of F_B can be approximated by an F -distribution with numerator and denominator degrees of freedom $df_1 = H_1 - 1$ and $df_2 = (H_1 m - 2)(H_1 - 1)$, respectively. Even though equation (5) defines a linear model, its error terms are not normally distributed. They are rather mean-corrected judgment order statistics from a normal distribution. Hence, the null distribution of F_B follows the exact F -distribution only if the ranks are assigned completely at random ($\rho_1 = \rho_2 = 0$). Otherwise, the null distribution of F_B follows an approximate F -distribution.

The null hypothesis of no treatment effect is rejected at a significance level, α , if F_B exceeds the critical value, $F_{df_1, df_2, \alpha}$. In this notation, $F_{df_1, df_2, \alpha}$ is the upper α^{th} quantile of the central F -distribution with numerator and denominator degrees of freedom $df_1 = H_1 - 1$ and $df_2 = (H_1 m - 2)(H_1 - 1)$, respectively.

We performed a simulation study of size 10,000 under model (5) to investigate the null distribution of F_B . The data were generated assuming the grand mean $\mu = 0$, no treatment effect, and no block effect. We let $\rho_1 = 0.7, 1$; $\rho_2 = 0.7, 1$; $H_1 = 2, 3, 4$; $m = 3, 5, 10$; $H_2 = 3, 5$; $d_2 = 2$; $\tau = 3$; and $ICC = 0.01, 0.2, 0.5, 0.8$. The choices of (γ, σ) used to obtain these ICC values were $(1, \sqrt{99})$, $(5, 10)$, $(1, 1)$, and $(10, 5)$, respectively.

For each combination of simulation parameters, we created a quantile-quantile (Q-Q) plot to see how well the F_{df_1, df_2} distribution approximates the null distribution of F_B . We present Q-Q plots for some of these simulation parameters in Figure 1 (similar results held for the combinations of simulation parameters not presented here). Each panel contains black and red points—the black points correspond to the exact F -distribution (i.e., ranking is completely at random), and the red points correspond to various degrees of ranking quality. The Q-Q plots for our proposed test statistic show approximate linearity, even when ρ_1 and ρ_2 are far from 0. The red and black points are also relatively close together in each panel. Hence, the F -distribution approximates the null distribution of F_B reasonably well. We note that there is more deviation between the points when $H_1 = 2$ and $m = 3$, but

this is likely because of the smaller denominator degrees of freedom, df_2 . An F -distribution with small df_2 is heavily right skewed, so extreme observations are more likely to occur in this case.

Figure 1: Q-Q plots of F_B with respect to $F_{H_1-1, (H_1 m-2)(H_1-1)}$ for an ORCRD with RSS at subsampling level

We conducted another simulation study of size 10,000 under model (5) to investigate Type I error rates. The data were generated assuming the grand mean $\mu = 0$, no treatment effect, and no block effect. We specified $\rho_1 = 0, 1$ and $\rho_2 = 0, 1$. For each combination of ρ_1 and ρ_2 , we let $H_1 = 3, 4$; $m = 3, 5, 10$; $H_2 = 3, 5$; $d_2 = 2$; $\tau = 3$; and $ICC = 0.01, 0.5$. The choices of (γ, σ) used to obtain these ICC values were $(1, \sqrt{99})$ and $(1, 1)$, respectively. We computed the empirical Type I error rates by finding the proportion of F_B values greater than the 95th percentile of a F_{df_1, df_2} distribution. Table 4 contains the Type I error rates for this simulation study. These Type I error rates are all close to 0.05, regardless of cluster level and subsampling level ranking quality. This empirical evidence implies that the null distribution of F_B can be approximated reasonably well by a central F -distribution for any correlation structure, various sample sizes, and various ICC values.

To investigate the empirical power of F_B , we conducted another simulation study of size 10,000. The data in this simulation study were generated assuming the overall mean $\mu = 0$ and no block effect. We performed ranking at both the cluster and subsampling levels of the ORCRD. The following simulation parameters were used: $\rho_1 = 0, 0.5, 0.75, 1$; $\rho_2 = 1$; $H_1 = 3, 4$; $m = 3, 5, 10$; $p = 6$ ($H_2 = 3, d_2 = 2$); $\tau = 3$; and $ICC = 0.01, 0.5$. The values of (γ, σ) used to obtain these ICC values were $(1, \sqrt{99})$ and $(1, 1)$, respectively. The nominal size of the hypothesis test was specified as $\alpha = 0.05$.

For each combination of simulation parameters, we computed the empirical power under the following alternative hypotheses:

$$H_a : \left\{ \beta_1 = -\frac{\Delta}{2}, \beta_2 = 0, \dots, \beta_{H_1-1} = 0, \beta_{H_1} = \frac{\Delta}{2} \right\},$$

Table 4: Type I error rates for the (approximate) F -test of treatment effect

H_1	m	H_2	d_2	ρ_1	ρ_2	$ICC = 0.01$	$ICC = 0.5$	ρ_1	ρ_2	$ICC = 0.01$	$ICC = 0.5$
						Type I error	Type I error			Type I error	Type I error
3	3	3	2	0	0	0.0495	0.0480	1	0	0.0504	0.0472
3	3	5	2	0	0	0.0519	0.0514	1	0	0.0504	0.0458
3	5	3	2	0	0	0.0499	0.0496	1	0	0.0518	0.0531
3	5	5	2	0	0	0.0465	0.0472	1	0	0.0543	0.0478
3	10	3	2	0	0	0.0512	0.0511	1	0	0.0507	0.0488
3	10	5	2	0	0	0.0493	0.0533	1	0	0.0489	0.0492
4	3	3	2	0	0	0.0545	0.0490	1	0	0.0492	0.0518
4	3	5	2	0	0	0.0495	0.0501	1	0	0.0491	0.0487
4	5	3	2	0	0	0.0486	0.0470	1	0	0.0500	0.0464
4	5	5	2	0	0	0.0504	0.0496	1	0	0.0488	0.0577
4	10	3	2	0	0	0.0496	0.0496	1	0	0.0488	0.0509
4	10	5	2	0	0	0.0457	0.0504	1	0	0.0486	0.0500
3	3	3	2	0	1	0.0474	0.0465	1	1	0.0511	0.0456
3	3	5	2	0	1	0.0461	0.0463	1	1	0.0516	0.0490
3	5	3	2	0	1	0.0490	0.0458	1	1	0.0496	0.0483
3	5	5	2	0	1	0.0483	0.0506	1	1	0.0508	0.0445
3	10	3	2	0	1	0.0504	0.0483	1	1	0.0496	0.0498
3	10	5	2	0	1	0.0473	0.0484	1	1	0.0490	0.0455
4	3	3	2	0	1	0.0457	0.0505	1	1	0.0501	0.0489
4	3	5	2	0	1	0.0548	0.0528	1	1	0.0503	0.0491
4	5	3	2	0	1	0.0489	0.0499	1	1	0.0485	0.0533
4	5	5	2	0	1	0.0495	0.0538	1	1	0.0511	0.0460
4	10	3	2	0	1	0.0513	0.0502	1	1	0.0505	0.0532
4	10	5	2	0	1	0.0482	0.0498	1	1	0.0509	0.0505

where $\Delta = \delta\sqrt{\gamma^2 + \sigma^2}$ and $\delta = 0(0.2)1$. The empirical power was computed as the proportion of F_B values greater than the 95th percentile of a F_{df_1, df_2} distribution, where $df_1 = H_1 - 1$ and $df_2 = (H_1 m - 2)(H_1 - 1)$. Figure 2 depicts the corresponding empirical power curves.

We note that the empirical power is an increasing function of the following parameters: δ , ρ_1 , H_1 (cluster level set size), and m (number of cluster units in each cell of the design). The empirical power is a decreasing function of ICC . We also note the following: better ranking quality at the cluster level has more of an impact on empirical power when ICC is large than when ICC is small. This is evident from Figure 2: the power curves in the second row are much more separated from each other than the power curves in the first row. This intuitively makes sense, since a larger ICC implies there is more variability between cluster units than when ICC is smaller. Thus, a good cluster level ranking quality (i.e., high ρ_1 value) is more important in reducing the unexplained cluster error variance in this case. Regardless of the value of ICC , when H_1 is fixed, the power curves for a larger value of ρ_1 lie above the power curves for a smaller value of ρ_1 .

4. Assessing Ranking Effectiveness and Estimating Model Parameters

As we observed in the previous section, the efficiency of an ORCRD depends on ranking quality. In general, the ranking quality may not be known a priori, but it can be estimated from the data. The EMS expressions in Table 3 suggest an F -statistic for the cluster level ranking group effect. This F -statistic is

$$F_C = \frac{MSC}{MSC\bar{E}}$$

Since ranking groups are not randomized, a formal F -test for the cluster ranking group effect may not be advisable—inference would not be reliable. However, the magnitude of

Figure 2: Empirical power curves of F_B

this F -statistic can be used to quantify the effectiveness of ranking at the cluster level. In particular, a large value of F_C suggests that ranking cluster units accounts for much of the variation in the response. Analogously, the magnitude of

$$F_S = \frac{MSS}{MSE}$$

can be used to quantify ranking effectiveness at the subsampling level.

The second method to examine ranking effectiveness involves estimating ρ_1 and ρ_2 . We use REML estimation to estimate these model parameters. We first note that the realized value of the REML estimator of τ , $\hat{\tau}$, can be found by fitting model (5) in R with the `lmer` function.

For the estimation of ρ_1 , we define $\eta_1 = \rho_1\gamma$. We estimate this quantity by

$$\hat{\eta}_1 = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k \bar{Y}_{k\dots}}{\sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2}. \quad (6)$$

Define θ_1^2 as

$$\theta_1^2 = \gamma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_1^2}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2 \right).$$

Solving this equation for γ and replacing the unknown parameters with their corresponding estimators, we obtain

$$\hat{\gamma} = \sqrt{\hat{\theta}_1^2 + \frac{(\hat{\eta}_1)^2}{H_1 - 1} \sum_{k=1}^{H_1} \phi_k^2}. \quad (7)$$

Note that the realized value of the REML estimator, $\hat{\theta}_1^2$, can be found by fitting model (5) in R with the *lmer* function.

Since $\eta_1 = \rho_1 \gamma$, we let

$$\hat{\rho}_1 = \frac{\hat{\eta}_1}{\hat{\gamma}},$$

where $\hat{\eta}_1$ and $\hat{\gamma}$ are as defined in equations (6) and (7), respectively. However, this estimator of ρ_1 can produce estimates bigger than 1, which is nonsensical in practice. Thus, we truncate $\hat{\rho}_1$ as follows:

$$\hat{\rho}_{1,trunc} = \begin{cases} \hat{\rho}_1, & \hat{\rho}_1 \leq 1 \\ 1, & \hat{\rho}_1 > 1 \end{cases}.$$

For the estimation of ρ_2 , we define $\eta_2 = \rho_2 \sigma$. We estimate this quantity by

$$\hat{\eta}_2 = \frac{\sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v \bar{Y}_{\dots v}}{\sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^2}. \quad (8)$$

Define θ_2^2 as

$$\theta_2^2 = \sigma^2 \left(1 - \frac{\rho_2^2}{H_2} \sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^2 \right).$$

Solving this equation for σ and replacing the unknown parameters with their corresponding estimators, we obtain

$$\hat{\sigma} = \sqrt{\hat{\theta}_2^2 + \frac{(\hat{\eta}_2)^2}{H_2} \sum_{v=1}^{H_2} \omega_v^2}. \quad (9)$$

Note that the realized value of the REML estimator, $\hat{\theta}_2^2$, can be found by fitting model (5) in R with the *lmer* function.

Since $\eta_2 = \rho_2 \sigma$, we let

$$\hat{\rho}_2 = \frac{\hat{\eta}_2}{\hat{\sigma}},$$

where $\hat{\eta}_2$ and $\hat{\sigma}$ are as defined in equations (8) and (9), respectively. However, this estimator of ρ_2 can produce estimates bigger than 1, which is nonsensical in practice. Thus, we truncate $\hat{\rho}_2$ as follows:

$$\hat{\rho}_{2,trunc} = \begin{cases} \hat{\rho}_2, & \hat{\rho}_2 \leq 1 \\ 1, & \hat{\rho}_2 > 1 \end{cases}.$$

The proposed estimators of ρ_1 and ρ_2 provide insight into the effectiveness of ranking at the cluster and subsampling level, respectively. In particular, a value of $\hat{\rho}_{1,trunc}$ close to 1 suggests that cluster level ranking group is an effective blocking factor. Hence, in this case, ranking cluster units accounts for much of the variation in the response. A value of $\hat{\rho}_{1,trunc}$ close to 0 indicates that the cluster level ranking group may not be a very useful blocking factor, in terms of reducing experimental variation. Analogous implications hold for $\hat{\rho}_{2,trunc}$ as well.

5. Concluding Remarks

Cluster randomized designs are often more practical than completely randomized designs; however, CRDs are generally less efficient. To overcome this deficiency, we propose the order restricted cluster randomized design (ORCRD)—a CRD that incorporates order restricted randomization at the cluster level and ranked set sampling at the subsampling level. The implementation of these techniques reduces between- and within-cluster variability, which ultimately improves upon the efficiency of a traditional CRD.

For the ORCRD, we propose a model that accounts for experimental sources of variation, such as ranking in stage 1 and 2 sampling. We calculate EMS expressions for each factor in the model. We use these expressions to develop inference for the treatment effect and assess ranking effectiveness. We end with a discussion on parameter estimation.

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